

Scientific article

UDC 81-13

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18824945

POLYPARADIGMATIC APPROACH TO COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS WITH LINK-VERBS

© 2026 N.Yu.Bessonov¹, E.V.Gordienko²

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration"

ORCID 0000-0002-8383-8065¹

ORCID 0000-0002-7759-0518²

Эта статья доступна по лицензии Attribution 4.0 International
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode.ru>

В статье представлены результаты анализа современных подходов к исследованию каузативных конструкций. Обосновывается возможность интеграции методологических основ доминирующих в настоящее время лингвистических парадигм, которые характеризуются значительным потенциалом в решении различных проблем семантического синтаксиса. Предлагаемый полипарадигмальный подход к сопоставительному исследованию каузативных конструкций с глаголами-связками способствует установлению общих и специфических характеристик семантики и структуры таких конструкций в разноструктурных языках. Интеграция методов конструкционной грамматики, когнитивной грамматики и когнитивной семантики в рамках полипарадигмального подхода позволяет установить сходства и отличия механизмов репрезентации в каузативных конструкциях информации, связанной с выражением причинно-следственных отношений, а также процедур структурирования знаний, используемых участниками коммуникативного процесса для формирования каузативного смысла. Обоснованный в работе комплексный подход позволяет выявить универсалии, касающиеся взаимосвязи формы, семантики и функции каузативов.

Ключевые слова: каузатив, каузативная конструкция, глагол-связка, конструкционная грамматика, когнитивная грамматика, когнитивная семантика, полипарадигмальный подход, семантический синтаксис.

For citation: Bessonov N.Yu. Polyparadigmatic Approach to Comparative Study of Causative Constructions with Link-Verbs / N.Yu. Bessonov, E.V. Gordienko // Bulletin of Donetsk National University. Series D. Philology and Psychology. — 2026. — No. 1. — P. 108–116. — <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18824945>.

Introduction. Causative constructions (CC) are studied in linguistics alongside other topical issues of semantic syntax [3; 10; 15; 16]. In a broad sense, a construction is understood as an ordered structure of grammatical units that form a unit of a hierarchically higher level. A causative construction is any construction expressing a causative situation. A basic causative situation (CS) is constituted by a simple event that causes another event, and the causative relations between these events. The causation relation is associated with the expression "*is the result of*". In this study CC is treated as any construction with the category of causation being its grammatical core, regardless of the nature of the semantic interpretation [8], for example: Eng. *The police evidence made him confess to the crime*. In this example, the agent of the causative situation is expressed by the noun *police*, the causative state - by the noun *evidence*, the object of the causative action - by the pronoun *him*, and the causative action - by the infinitive *confess*. The verb *make*, that links the causative situation with the one, which is being caused, is the CC main element. The linking verbs with the broadest causative meaning in English are the verbs *let, make, get, have*, while in Russian these are the verbs *позволять, разрешать, заставлять, запрещать, вынуждать*, and some others. The grammatical CC is

related to the semantic CS. According to the approach by V. Nedyalkov and G. Silnitsky [9], which formed the study methodological basis, the causative situation (or macrosituation) consists of two microsituations: the causative situation (antecedent), the caused situation (consequent), and the causation relationship, i.e., the relationship linking the causative and caused situations. The typical CC model includes two elementary participants (the causator and the object of causation), the causative action expressed by the link-verb, and the result of causation. The causal action is always expressed explicitly; other elements can be expressed both explicitly or implicitly. Thus, the CC syntactic structure does not always coincide with the semantic structure. Depending on the language type, this model can have the following modes of expression: 1) lexical, 2) analytical, 3) morphological.

Despite the advances of linguistics and linguists' attention to the syntactic units of language, the underlying mechanisms by which they represent information, the knowledge structuring procedures used by speakers to form their meaning, the factors influencing this process remain unexplored [4, p. 535]. The interpretive nature of modern linguistic studies necessitates further systematization of accumulated knowledge in the field of causative theory and causative constructions. The relevance of this work is also due to the insufficient level of study of the specific linguistic implementation of constructions with causative verbs in non-cognate languages. Thus, the results of the analysis of modern approaches to the study of causative verbs and the substantiation of the possibility of integrating the methodological foundations of currently dominant linguistic paradigms show significant potential.

This contribution objective is to substantiate a multi-paradigm approach to the comparative study of constructions with link-verbs, which will facilitate the identification of isomorphic and allomorphic semantic and structural features of constructions with causative link-verbs in non-closely cognate languages.

The study focuses on constructions with linking causative verbs (CV) in English and Russian, excerpted from works of English, American, and Russian fiction of the 20th century. The following methods of linguistic analysis are applied: *comparative analysis*, aimed at establishing similarities and differences in the semantics and structure of CC with link-verbs; *componential analysis*, enabling to identify integral and differential features in the CV semantics; *modeling the CV semantics by means of interpretation formulas* in order to describe in detail the semantic content of the constructions under study; *syntactic analysis*, aimed at considering the features of the CV formal organization; and *contextual analysis*, which makes it possible to identify the explicit and implicit means of expressing components in CC with link-verbs.

Results and discussion. Modern linguistics approaches language analysis in the interdisciplinary and anthropocentric way. Linguistic anthropocentrism is the dominant principle of modern research, since "the human is present throughout the entire space of language" [7, p. 3] (see also [5]). In this respect, a comprehensive approach to considering language units and categories of various types appears relevant in modern linguistic research, including typological and comparative studies. Their various aspects are being focused on [6; 13]. In this study, the suggested approach integrates the conceptual apparatus and methods of typological and comparative linguistics, as well as the methods of functional-semantic and cognitive linguistics, and constructional grammar.

Within the framework of the present research a significant contribution to the development of the causative theory by the Leningrad Typological Group, i.e. the collective monograph "Typology of Causative Constructions" [14], should be pointed out to. The ideas expressed in this work by V. Nedyalkov, G. Silnitsky, A. Kholodovich, and V. Khrakovsky on grammatical constructions expressing various meanings of the category of causativity served as the methodological basis for the present study.

We consider it necessary to integrate the typological approach with the research traditions of cognitive grammar, cognitive semantics, and constructional grammar. These rapidly developing areas of cognitive linguistics differ in their conceptual apparatus, approaches, research subjects, and analytical procedures. Nevertheless, they share a common "striving to explain linguistic facts and linguistic categories and, in one way or another, to correlate linguistic forms with their mental representations and with the experience they reflect as structures of knowledge" [12, p. 19]. Cognitive linguistics' focus on semantic issues stems from its methodological proximity to linguistic semantics, which explains the trend to speak of cognitive semantics rather than cognitive linguistics or grammar. It should be emphasized that a cognitive description of only the lexical-semantic system of language does not provide a complete understanding of the way the cognitive experience of a linguistic personality is reflected in the worldview. The multifaceted nature of the relationship between a person and a language necessitates cognitive research in grammar, with the focus on grammatical categories and their functions, which depend on human cognitive activity related to the information processing, storage, use, and transformation. Thus, a comparative study of causative constructions in non-cognate languages is more fruitful in case of the integrated application of comparative semantic-cognitive approach, and construction grammar methodology.

The treatment of causality within the framework of cognitive grammar is of particular interest, since constructions (including the causative ones) are generally considered to be traditional combinations of form and function that are constructed rather than learned based on the information input, along with general cognitive, pragmatic, and other constraints [1]. Constructions are viewed as linguistic structures in which some aspects of form or function are not motivated by their components. Furthermore, even fully motivated and absolutely predictable structures are now called constructions if, due to their frequency, they have acquired a stable status as linguistic units. This updated approach to defining constructions underlies the relevance of grammatical models based on usage [2]. Thus, the integration of ideas of cognitive grammar and cognitive semantics suggested in the present research appears relevant.

Alongside the approach of the St. Petersburg (Leningrad) typological school, the methodological basis of this study grounded on the works by typologist and cognitive grammarian L. Talmi ([18; 19]). These works are of interest for their focus on such issues as the syntax of complex sentences, the semantics of causative expressions, and the semantics and syntax of verbs of motion. The theoretical constructs proposed in L. Talmi's articles, in particular his typology of causatives, as well as the empirical material presented in his works, deserve a special attention. The main postulate is the recognition that the structural and functional features of a natural language can be explained by appealing to cognitive structures and processes.

The core idea of L. Talmi's semantic typology can be presented as follows: causative and other situations from the category of force dynamics are conceptualized as basic force-dynamic situations, in which one force (the antagonist) is linked by a certain relationship to another force (the agonist). Both of these forces have an inherent tendency toward rest or movement. Depending on whether the antagonist and the agonist, and, accordingly, their forces, are opposed, the resulting situation can be either of rest or movement [18]. The principle of force dynamics underlies the understanding of causation. According to this principle, the interaction of various entities with one another is interpreted in terms of force and is reduced to its characteristic manifestations, such as the direct demonstration of force, resistance to force, overcoming resistance, blocking force, eliminating blocking, etc.

In P. Parshin's view, L. Talmi's research program stands completely apart: his works are based on the analysis of linguistic empirics, and his research methodology "is practically a classical linguistic experiment in L. Shcherba's sense, on which almost all modern semantics is based: this

is the clarification of the way one can and cannot say - with the significant modification that Talmi is interested above all in its reason" [11, p. 89]. L. Talmi's most important impact is the creation of an empirically substantiated theory of cognitive super categories (for example, plexity or force dynamics), in relation to which the categories of aspect, number, causation, etc. are particular realizations. It is relevant to mention that the typological focus of L. Talmi's works, his interest in cognitive categories are close to the linguistic views of A. Kholodovich and his school, T. Bulygina and others, since the Russian linguistic tradition is characterized by "fundamental semantics" (P. Parshin's term [11]) and attention to empirical material.

As it has already been pointed out, the grammatical causative construction is related to the semantic causative situation. According to M. Shibatani, the definition of a causative construction presupposes the definition of the causative situation expressed by this construction [17, p. 1]. Two events form a causative situation if two conditions are met: 1) the relationship between the two events is characterized by the speaker believing that the caused event occurred after the causative event; 2) the relationship between the causative and caused events is characterized by the speaker believing that the occurrence of the caused event depends entirely on the occurrence of the causative event [17, pp. 1–2]. L. Talmi shares M. Shibatani's view that a basic causative situation consists of a simple event that causes another event and the causative relations between these events [19, p. 52]. This semantic phenomenon can be syntactically presented by one of two fundamental structures [19, p. 53] (see the scheme below):

Scheme. Structure of a basic causative situation

According to the scheme, the causative situation can be presented in the form of the following propositions: S (event) CAUSE S (event) and S (event) RESULT FROM S (event), where S (event) in the left denotes the causative event, S (event) in the right — the caused event. The caused event functions as a figure or image, and the causative event serves as the cause of the entire situation (these elements are presented in a similar sequence in the underlying linguistic structure). The causation relation is associated with the expression "is the result of". The domain of the causative event is identified with the object, functioning as a figure or image of the caused event. The object is connected with the image of the caused event by relations of force contact, and this contact can arise or be maintained, but not interrupted. According to L. Talmi, these characteristics can be represented by the deep structure morpheme ACT ON [19, p. 67]. The figure and objects of the caused event perform similar functions in relation to the entire causative situation, and the image of the object of the causative event functions as its instrument (INSTRUMENT). The caused event is initiated by the causative event, and, conversely, the caused event will not occur if there is no causative event. The image of the caused event is characterized by a natural tendency to resist, which is overcome by the force of the instrument of the causative event. The caused event can also be associated with a vector arising as a result of the combined action of the vectors of the image and instrument. The causative situation can be momentary or prolonged, and in each case, it can be characterized by allomorphic characteristics. In terms of duration, the causative event is similar to the caused event [19].

L. Talmy singles out a number of types of causative situations, among which: resulting-event causative, causing-event causative, autonomous events, author causative, agent causative, extended causation, onset causation, effectuating causation, enabling causation, “purpose” situation, inductive causation, and chain-of-action causation [18]. L. Talmy distinguishes between the concepts of agent (A), author (Au), and experiencer (U), for example: *I (A) hid my pen somewhere in the kitchen; I (Au) hid my pen somewhere in the kitchen; I (U) hid my pen somewhere in the kitchen.*

The classification of causative relations by many criteria includes various types. It can be logically assumed that all types are observed in the causative constructions with link-verbs that constitute the study empirical material. However, as the empirical material shows, the different types of constructions under study are characterized by different frequency value.

1. By **complexity and differing as to the element foregrounded (appearing initially)**, a distinction is made between autonomous events, resulting-event causative (basic causative), causing-event causative, instrument causative, author causative - i.e., with unintended outcome, and agent causative - i.e., with intended outcome. The constructions with causative link-verbs in English most often represent events occurring as a result of a resulting-event causative (basic causative), for example: *Her sudden movement made the cup turn over* [29].

2. According to **the number of links in a serial causative chain**, autonomous events, two- and three-event causative chains are distinguished. The most frequent types of causative chains are autonomous (Eng. *The smell made him vomit* [24], Rus. *рус. Надо дать знать, чтобы их взяли в колонию* (К.Г. Паустовский. Повесть о жизни. Книга скитаний, 1963) [20] and two-event (Eng. *There's always a goat; the one that's going to get its throat cut* [21]; Rus. *Тогда только силою можно заставить делать то, что человек считает нелепым и то только на самое короткое время* (Л.Н. Толстой. Неизбежный переворот, 1909) [20]).

3. According to **the degree of continuity in a causative chain**, a distinction is made between continuous and discontinuous causative chains. The sample material showed that the most frequent in both English and Russian are discontinuous chains, for example: Eng. *The man made the dogs push the sledge with even more power by hitting them with his stick* [26]; Rus. *Затем вновь наступила тишина, и в этой тишине папа произнес отчетливо и жестко: «Никто не заставит нас свернуть с намеченного пути...»* (Б. Окуджава. Упраздненный театр, 1989-1993) [20].

4. According to **the coextensiveness of the causing event with the resulting event**, a distinction is made between extended causation and onset causation. The second type, namely the onset causation, proved to be the most frequent one, for example: Eng. *The big man got the spitz angry before the fight and then watched him taking the rivals down one after another* [26]; Rus. *Признаюсь, гордость не позволила мне сделать это одному, оставив русского* (А.С. Грин. Дьявол Оранжевых Вод, 1913) [20].

5. According to **the overcoming of resistance versus the removal of blockage**, a distinction is made between effectuating causation and enabling causation. Among the examples in the empirical corpus, the enabling causation type prevailed, for example: Eng.: *I let Bruno do all my business work* [25]; Rus. *Олешке надо дать выгуляться, пускай с него пена сойдет* (М. Горький. Дело Артамоновых, 1924-1925) [20].

6. According to **the scope of intention on the part of a sentient entity**, a distinction should be made between agent causation, author causation, and “undergoer” causation. The agent causation turned out to be the most frequent type, for example: Eng. *Either you have lost the letter or you didn't have it to lose in the first place* [30]; Rus. *Люди, которых он, по его словам, представляет, считают своим непреложным долгом обусловить ликвидацию всего того, что было связано — и может быть в будущем связано — с СС и НСДАП* (Ю. Семенов. Семнадцать мгновений весны, 1968) [20].

7. According to *knowledge of outcome*, a distinction is made between the agent causation and the “purpose” situation. In our case, both types are characterized by the same frequency value, for example: agent causation (Eng. *John had the dogs calm down by shouting at them* [27]; Rus. — *Что же вы молчите?.. Немедленно нужно дать знать шефу полиции. — Товарищ дорогой, вы с ума сошли!* (А.Н. Толстой. Гиперболоид инженера Гарина, 1925-1927, 1937) [20] and “purpose” situation (Eng. *In order to be on the safe side, Buck made the rival reach him from the side* [23]; Rus. *Этот мужичишка заставил на мельнице работать вместо ветра медведя, чтобы не платить налога, а сам скулил всегда по-батрацки и ел с бабой под одеялом* (А.П. Платонов. Котлован, 1930) [20].

8. According to *the presence of internal self-direction*, a distinction is made between an autonomous event and causation of the action of an agent. This type of CC with link-verbs is not found in the languages under study.

9. According to *the presence of self-directedness in mid-causal-chain*, the agent causation and inducive causation (caused agency) are distinguished. The empirical corpus includes quite a number of examples of both types: agent causation (Eng. *The hostess let the housemaid relax by saying a few soothing words* [23]; Rus. *Надеюсь, ты не заставишь меня краснеть за тебя перед господином Ананасовым* (В.П. Катаев. Миллион терзаний, 1930) [20] and inducive causation (caused agency) (Eng. *Don't bother to make servants come up to us — we are alone here* [28]; Rus. *Единственное, чего он не мог бы перенести, по его словам, — это попасть в руки фашистам и позволить им издеваться над собой* (К.Г. Паустовский. Повесть о жизни. Книга скитаний, 1963 [20]).

10. According to *the number of occurrences of self-directedness along a causal chain*, a distinction is made between two-, three-, and four-member chains of actions. Three-member chains are most typical of constructions with causative link-verbs, for example: Eng. *Oh, do let me help to undo it* [22]; Rus. *Он даже вынужден был позволить всем по очереди посмотреть, что там происходит, прежде чем они тронулись дальше* (А.А. Фадеев. Молодая гвардия, 1943-1951) [20].

The analysis of the semantic causative types classification indicates the absence of an unambiguous interpretation of the causative situation itself, since its interpretation is influenced by various internal factors. The deep semantic meaning of the verb *cause* can be conveyed by combining the meaning of any verbal lexeme with at least five deep causative verbs such as RESULT, EVENT, INSTRUMENT, AUTHOR, AGENT.

Conclusion. The verb regular lexical and grammatical relations, particularly the causative ones, alongside the primary lexical semantics, determine the nature of its syntactic construction. On the one hand, the application of the relevant methods of comparative linguistics, construction grammar, and cognitive linguistics enabled to establish the invariant meaning of the category of causativity. On the other hand, various shades of meaning of this category that manifest themselves in the context have been identified, which is due to the different structure of the languages under analysis. The suggested polyparadigmatic approach made it possible to establish similarities and differences in the mechanisms of representing information in cognitive complexes related to the expression of cause-and-effect relationships, as well as the knowledge structuring procedures used by participants in the communicative process to express the causative meaning. The integrated approach proposed in this paper allows us to identify universals concerning the relationship between the form, semantics, and function of causatives. The advantage of the comparative approach lies in clarification of various linguistic aspects of such a universal category as causativity. In addition to postulating a formal model, the polyparadigmatic approach allows for a more precise capture and interpretation of semantic meanings and shades of meaning. Within the framework of the comparative research,

it is relevant to thoroughly examine the semantic features of constructions with causative link-verbs, taking into account various parameters, as well as to identify universal characteristics, and gaps in the semantic organization of causative verbs in non-cognate languages, to interpret similarities and differences, and to formulate probabilistic implications.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Бабайцева В.В. Современный русский язык: в 3-х ч. / В.В. Бабайцева, Л.Ю. Максимов. — М.: Просвещение, 1981. — Ч. 3. Синтаксис. Пунктуация. — 281 с.
2. Балли Ш. Общая лингвистика и вопросы французского языка / Ш. Балли. — М.: Издательство «Едиториал УРСС», 2009. — Серия «Лингвистическое наследие XX века». — 416 с.
3. Всеволодова М.В. Теория функционально-коммуникативного синтаксиса / М.В. Всеволодова. — М.: Изд-во МГУ, 2000. — 502 с.
4. Давыдова Е.И. О синтаксических структурах как способе репрезентации знаний в языке / Е.И. Давыдова // Когнитивные исследования языка: мат-лы Всеросс. науч. конф., 11–12 апр. 2013 г. / отв. ред. вып. Л.А. Фурс. — М.: Ин-т языкознания РАН; Тамбов: Издательский дом ТГУ им. Г.Р. Державина, 2013. — Вып. XIV: Когнитивная лингвистика: итоги, перспективы. — С. 534–537.
5. Карасик В.И. Языковое проявление личности: монография / В.И. Карасик; Научно-исследовательская лаборатория «Аксиологическая лингвистика». — [2-е изд., стер.]. — Москва: Гнозис, 2015. — 383 с.
6. Кибрик А.А. Когнитивный анализ дискурса: локальная структура / А.А. Кибрик // Язык и мысль: Современная когнитивная лингвистика / сост. А.А. Кибрик, А.Д. Кошелев и др. — М.: Языки славянской культуры, 2015. — С. 595–634.
7. Логический анализ языка. Образ человека в культуре и языке / отв. ред. Н.Д. Арутюнова, И.Б. Левонтина. — Москва: Индрик, 1999. — 422 с.
8. Неद्याков В.П. Каузативные конструкции в немецком языке. Аналитический каузатив / В.П. Неद्याков. — Ленинград: Изд-во «Наука», Ленинградское отделение, 1971. — 179 с.
9. Неद्याков В.П. Типология морфологического и лексического каузативов / В.П. Неद्याков, Г.Г. Сильницкий // Типология каузативных конструкций. Морфологический каузатив. — Ленинград: Изд-во «Наука», Ленинградское отделение, 1969. — С. 20–50.
10. Падучева Е.В. О семантике синтаксиса: Материалы к трансформационной грамматике русского языка: монография / Е.В. Падучева. — М.: Ленанд, 2023. — 300 с. (Серия «Лингвистическое наследие XX века»). ISBN: 978-5-9710-2955-7.
11. Паршин П.Б. Об исследовательской программе Леонарда Талми / П.Б. Паршин // Вестник Московского университета. Сер. 9. Филология. — 1999. — № 1. — С. 88–91.
12. Пименова М.В. Концептуальные исследования. Введение: учеб. пособ. / М.В. Пименова, О.Н. Кондратьева. — М.: Флинта, Наука, 2011. — 176 с.
13. Плунгян В.А. Введение в грамматическую семантику: Грамматические значения и грамматические системы языков мира / В.А. Плунгян. — М.: РГГУ, 2011. — 672 с.
14. Типология каузативных конструкций (морфологический каузатив) / под ред. А.А. Холодовича. — Ленинград: Изд-во «Наука», Ленинградское отделение, 1969. — 312 с.
15. Bierwisch M. The Event Structure of CAUSE and BECOME / M. Bierwisch // Event Arguments: Foundations and Applications. — Tübingen: Niermeyer, 2005. — P. 11–44.
16. Dikken M. den On the syntax of verb-particle, triadic, and causative constructions / M. Dikken. — New York: Oxford University Press, 1995. — 288 p.
17. Shibatani M. The Grammar of Causative Constructions; a Conspectus / M. Shibatani // Syntax and Semantics. — New York: Academic Press, 1976. — Vol. 6. — P. 1–40.
18. Talmy L. Force dynamics in language and cognition / L. Talmy // Cognitive Science. — 1988. — 12. — P. 49–100.
19. Talmy L. Semantic causative types / L. Talmy // Syntax and semantics 6: the grammar of causative constructions. — New York: Academic Press, 1976. — P. 43–116.

СПИСОК ИСТОЧНИКОВ

20. Национальный корпус русского языка. URL: <https://ruscorpora.ru> (дата обращения 17.01.2026).
21. Butler G. Coffin in Fashion. London: Fontana Press, 1990. 224 p.
22. Carroll L. Alice's Adventures in Wonderland / L. Carroll // English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
23. Doyle A.C. The Adventure of the Copper Beeches / A.C. Doyle // English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.

24. Henry O. The Four Million / O. Henry // English and American Literature. English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
25. Lyall G. The Conduct of Major Maxim. Sevenoaks, Kent: Hodder and Stoughton Ltd, 1982. 308 p.
26. London J. The Call of the Wild / J. London // English and American Literature / CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
27. London J. White Fang / J. London // English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
28. Mansfield K. Bliss / K. Mansfield // English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
29. Mansfield K. The Garden-Party / K. Mansfield // English and American Literature. — CD-ROM. P. 3. Digitale Bibliothek Band 59. Berlin, 2003.
30. Stoppard T. Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are dead. London: Faber and Faber Ltd., 1986. — 92 p.

REFERENCES

1. Babaytseva, V.V., Maksimov, L.Yu. (1981). *Sovremennyy russkiy yazyk [The Modern Russian Language]: v 3-kh ch.* Moscow: Prosveschenie. Ch. 3. Sintaksis. Punktatsiya. (In Russian).
2. Balli, Sh. (2009). *Obschaya lingvistika i voprosy frantsuzskogo yazyka [General Linguistics and Issues of the French Language]*. Moscow: Izdatel'stvo «Editorial URSS». Seriya «Lingvisticheskoe nasledie XX veka». (In Russian).
3. Vsevolodova, M.V. (2000). *Teoriya funktsional'no-kommunikativnogo sintaksisa [Theory of Functional and Communicative Syntax]*. Moscow: Izd-vo MGU. (In Russian).
4. Davydova, E.I. (2013). *O sintaksicheskikh strukturakh kak sposobe reprezentatsii znaniy v yazyke [On Syntactic Structures as Way of Knowledge Representation in Language]*. In L.A. Furs (Ed.), *Kognitivnye issledovaniya yazyka: mat-ly Vseross. nauch. konf., 11–12 apr. 2013 g.* Moscow: In-t yazykoznaniiya RAN; Tambov: Izdatel'skiy dom TGU im. G.R. Derzhavina. Iss. XIV: *Kognitivnaya lingvistika: itogi, perspektivy*, 534–537. (In Russian).
5. Karasik, V.I. (2015). *Yazykovoe proyavlenie lichnosti [Language Representation of Personality]: monografiya. 2-e izd., ster.* Moscow: Gnozis. (In Russian).
6. Kibrik, A.A. (2015). *Kognitivnyy analiz diskursa: lokal'naya struktura [Cognitive Analysis of Discourse: Local Structure]*. In A.A. Kibrik, A.D. Koshelev i dr. (Eds.), *Yazyk i mysl': Sovremennaya kognitivnaya lingvistika*. Moscow: Yazyki slavyanskoy kul'tury, 595–634. (In Russian).
7. Arutyunova, N.D., Levontina, I.B. (Eds.). (1999). *Logicheskiy analiz yazyka. Obraz cheloveka v kul'ture i yazyke [Logical Analysis of Language. Image of Person in Culture and Language]*. Moscow: Indrik. (In Russian).
8. Nedyalkov, V.P. (1971). *Kauzativnye konstruksii v nemetskom yazyke. Analiticheskiy kauzativ [Causative Constructions in German. Analytical Causative]*. Leningrad: Izd-vo «Nauka», Leningradskoe otdelenie. (In Russian).
9. Nedyalkov, V.P., Sil'nitskiy, G.G. (1969). *Tipologiya morfologicheskogo i leksicheskogo kauzativov [Typology of Morphological and Lexical Causatives]*. In *Tipologiya kauzativnykh konstruksiy. Morfologicheskii kauzativ*. Leningrad: Izd-vo «Nauka», Leningradskoe otdelenie, 20–50. (In Russian).
10. Paducheva, E.V. (2023). *O semantike sintaksisa: Materialy k transformatsionnoy grammatike russkogo yazyka [On Semantics of Syntax: Materials on Transformation Grammar of Russian]: monografiya*. Moscow: Lenand. (Seriya «Lingvisticheskoe nasledie XX veka»). ISBN: 978-5-9710-2955-7. (In Russian).
11. Parshin, P.B. (1999). *Ob issledovatel'skoy programme Leonarda Talmi [On L. Talmi's Research Programme]*. In *Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Ser. 9. Filologiya*, no 1, 88–91. (In Russian).
12. Pimenova, M.V. Kondrat'eva, O.N. (2011). *Kontseptual'nye issledovaniya. Vvedenie [Conceptual Research. Introduction]: ucheb. posob.* Moscow: Flinta, Nauka. (In Russian).
13. Plungyan, V.A. (2011). *Vvedenie v grammaticheskuyu semantiku: Grammaticheskie znacheniya i grammaticheskie sistemy yazykov mira [Introduction into Semantics of Grammar: Grammatical Meanings and Grammatical Systems of World Languages]*. Moscow: RGGU. (In Russian).
14. Kholodovich, A.A. (Ed.). (1969). *Tipologiya kauzativnykh konstruksiy (morfologicheskii kauzativ) [Typology of Causative Constructions (Morphological Causative)]*. Leningrad: Izd-vo «Nauka», Leningradskoe otdelenie. (In Russian).
15. Bierwisch, M. (2005). *The Event Structure of CAUSE and BECOME*. In *Event Arguments: Foundations and Applications*. Tübingen: Niermeyer. (In English).
16. Dikken, M. den (1995). *On the syntax of verb-particle, triadic, and causative constructions*. New York: Oxford University Press. (In English).

17. Shibatani, M. (1976). The Grammar of Causative Constructions; a Conspectus. In *Syntax and Semantics*. New York: Academic Press, vol. 6, 1–40. (In English).
18. Talmy, L. (1988). Force dynamics in language and cognition. In *Cognitive Science*, 12, 49–100. (In English).
19. Talmy, L. (1976). Semantic causative types. In *Syntax and semantics 6: the grammar of causative constructions*. New York: Academic Press, 43–116. (In English).

Поступила в редакцию 10.02.2026 г.

POLYPARADIGMATIC APPROACH TO COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS WITH LINK-VERBS

N.Y. Bessonov, E.V. Gordienko

This article deals with the results of the analysis of modern approaches to the study of causative constructions. It substantiates the possibility of integrating the methodological grounds of currently dominant linguistic paradigms, which offer a significant potential for solving versatile problems of semantic syntax. The suggested polyparadigmatic approach to the comparative study of causative constructions with link-verbs facilitates the identification of isomorphic and specific characteristics in the semantics and structure of such constructions in cognate and non-cognate languages. The integration of constructional grammar and cognitive grammar methods within the framework of the polyparadigmatic approach enables to establish similarities and differences in the mechanisms of representation in causative constructions of information related to the expression of cause-and-effect relationships, as well as the knowledge structuring procedures used by participants in the communicative process to form causative meaning. The integrated approach substantiated in this contribution makes it possible to identify universals concerning the relationship between the form, semantics, and function of causatives.

Key words: causative, causative construction, link-verb, constructional grammar, cognitive grammar, cognitive semantics, polyparadigmatic approach, semantic syntax.

Бессонов Никита Юрьевич.

Кандидат филологических наук.
Российская академия народного хозяйства
и государственной службы при Президенте
Российской Федерации, г. Москва.
Доцент Центра лингвистики
и профессиональной коммуникации
Департамента языковой подготовки
Общеакадемического факультета.
Старший научный сотрудник научно-
исследовательской лаборатории
«Лингвобезопасность и психология
информационного воздействия».
ORCID 0000-0002-8383-8065.
E-mail: bessonov-ny@ranepa.ru.

Гордиенко Елена Витальевна.

Кандидат филологических наук.
Российская академия народного хозяйства
и государственной службы при Президенте
Российской Федерации, г. Москва.
Доцент Центра лингвистики
и профессиональной коммуникации
Департамента языковой подготовки
Общеакадемического факультета.
ORCID 0000-0002-7759-0518.
E-mail: gordienko-ev@ranepa.ru.

Bessonov Nikita Yurievich.

Candidate of Philology.
Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy
and Public Administration, Moscow.

Associate Professor of the Centre for Linguistics and
Professional Communication for the Department of Foreign
Languages of the General Academic Faculty.

Senior Researcher of the Research Laboratory «Linguistic
Security and Psychology of Information Impact».

ORCID 0000-0002-8383-8065.

E-mail: bessonov-ny@ranepa.ru.

Gordienko Elena Vitalievna.

Candidate of Philology.
Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy
and Public Administration, Moscow.

Associate Professor of the Centre for Linguistics and
Professional Communication for the Department of Foreign
Languages of the General Academic Faculty.

ORCID 0000-0002-7759-0518.

E-mail: gordienko-ev@ranepa.ru.